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Introduction

This document provides an overview of the current structure and functioning of the [European Reference Genome Atlas](#) and how you can start participating. It is a starting point for new members as it aims to serve as a reference to clarify Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs). If your question is not addressed here, do not hesitate to reach out to us at contact@erga-biodiversity.eu. We will do our best to put you in contact with the right person!

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

I. Our Community

1. What is ERGA?

The [European Reference Genome Atlas](#) is a community of peers working to advance the generation of reference genomes for European biodiversity. The majority of ERGA members work directly with biodiversity-related topics that can benefit from genomes, while some of them are exclusively dedicated to genome data generation, assembly, annotation, or management. Nonetheless, all ERGA members share the common view that reference genomes are crucial for a deep understanding of biodiversity. Our community is mostly made up of researchers with very diverse expertise and backgrounds working on the European continent or interested in European biodiversity. ERGA also represents the European node of the larger [Earth BioGenome Project](#).

2. What are ERGA's main goals?

ERGA has various core objectives, including to:

- Create and consolidate a collaborative and interdisciplinary network of scientists across Europe and Associated countries to deliver the most complete reference genome sequences;
- Connect relevant genomic / sequencing infrastructures across Europe and Associated countries following an inclusive, accessible, and distributed model for genome sequence generation and analysis that can increase dynamically;
- Develop open-access guidelines and best practices for state-of-the-art reference genome sequence generation, and disseminate them through training and knowledge transfer;
- Connect ERGA with other BioGenome initiatives working on European species to maximise synergies and accelerate scientific outcomes;
- Establish links **between scientists, stakeholders, and citizens** to increase trust in the scientific process and ensure that genomic research reflects societal needs and perspectives.

Check our [Governance Document](#) to learn more about ERGA's structure.

3. How can I get involved and contribute to ERGA?

There are many ways in which you can get involved and contribute to ERGA.

The first action you will need to take is to [register as a new ERGA member](#). Membership is free of charge and will ensure you receive our [monthly newsletter](#) and information about upcoming events and meetings. Once you become a member, you will have easy access to all **ERGA meetings**. We recommend joining our monthly [plenary meetings](#), as these are a good starting point for you to get to know the community.

If you want to contribute to ERGA's mission and share your knowledge and expertise on a specific step of the genome generation process, consider interacting with or joining one of the [ERGA committees](#). Each committee has its way of operating and meets monthly. If you want to participate, we recommend you send an email to the committee's address to make sure that you are added to their communication channels and learn the best opportunities to contribute.

If you are working on a genome project of a European eukaryotic species and would like to get an ERGA stamp of approval to show that your reference genome meets all high-quality standards, you are welcome to associate it with ERGA as a "Community Genome". Check [this page](#) for more information on this procedure.

4. Is ERGA open to everyone?

Yes! To become a member, all you have to do is fill in a short and free-of-charge [registration form](#). Your personal data will be treated confidentially.

5. Is ERGA a financed project?

No, ERGA is not a scientific society or a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). **We are a bottom-up initiative of scientists interested in advancing the generation and application of reference genomes for European biodiversity.** Our activities include applying for grants to get funding to achieve this goal.

6. Is ERGA associated with the Earth BioGenome Project (EBP)?

Yes, ERGA is the European node of the [Earth BioGenome Project](#) (EBP). We are in constant dialogue and synergy with the EBP, seeking to align our efforts and goals for the benefit of our scientific community.

7. What are the main "bodies" that compose ERGA and how can I make contact?

The main driving force of ERGA is its broad community of members. However, we also have an administrative structure in place, which includes the ERGA Council, an Executive Board (EB) elected by the council, and ten ERGA Committees. To reach out to the Council members, Executive Board, or any of the committees, please use the email addresses listed on the ["Community" page of our website](#).

8. Am I allowed to join the Committee Meetings?

Yes, the committee meetings are open to all ERGA members - regardless of career stage or field of expertise. However, the only requirement is for you to sign up using the [registration form](#). Check [this table](#) for a list of all committees and their respective email addresses. If you wish to join a committee, please send them an email to receive all relevant minutes and links. You can check the dates and times of upcoming meetings on the [ERGA Calendar](#).

[For more information about how committees function, please refer to the committee's section below.](#)

9. How can I reach out to request support from ERGA?

You can use the [ERGA Support Request form](#) or write directly to one of the ERGA email addresses listed [here](#).

10. Is there a more informal way to chat with other ERGA members?

Yes, the [ERGA KeyBase team](#) is the place for that. Feel free to browse through the existing channels and join the ones that interest you the most. Each committee has a channel - that's a good place to introduce yourself and stay informed about the next activities/meetings.

11. I don't have so much time to attend multiple ERGA meetings but I still want to have an overview of what is going on. How can I stay up-to-date?

As soon as you [register as a member](#), you will start receiving our monthly [newsletter](#) which will keep you informed about all the most important updates, events, and opportunities going on in the community. Another way to stay informed is to attend the monthly [Plenary meetings](#) on the [third Monday of each month at 3 pm CET](#), in which ERGA committees and Affiliated Projects will be presenting their updates and the community has a space to ask questions or start discussions. The agenda of the plenary is announced a few days before the meeting through the mailing list.

12. What is the difference between the Plenary and Council meetings?

The monthly [Plenary Meetings](#) gather the whole community and are the primary forum through which announcements are made to the community; discussions and debates are conducted on topic-oriented presentations.

The ERGA Council meetings, on the other hand, are generally reserved to Council members. For more details on the Council and its composition, refer to the [Governance Document](#).

13. What are some of the differences between ERGA, EBP and Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE)?

	ERGA	EBP	BGE
Type	Community	Community / Project	Project / Consortium
Focus	Reference Genomes	Reference Genomes	Boosting Biodiversity Genomics in Europe
Scope	European	Global	European
Timeframe	Open-ended	Open-ended	2022 - 2026
Website	www.erga-biodiversity.eu/	www.earthbiogenome.org/	biodiversitygenomics.eu/

14. Can ERGA finance my reference genome project?

No, at the moment ERGA does not have core funding to directly fund projects. Whenever interesting funding opportunities come up - for example through the [Biodiversity Genomics Europe \(BGE\)](#) Project - we announce them to the community. ERGA can also provide you with a letter of support signed by the Executive Board if you wish to write a grant application that includes reference genome sequencing. This type of request can be made through the [support request form](#).

15. Can I associate my “independent” genome to ERGA?

Yes! ERGA is an umbrella name that covers many different projects. We call genomes produced “independently” by individual research groups “Community Genomes”. [Here you will find a detailed step-by-step guide on how to associate your genome with ERGA.](#)

16. What is the policy of ERGA on data?

Check our [Open Data Policy](#). If you have questions or concerns about our data policy, please reach out to the IT & Infrastructure committee at itinfra@erga-biodiversity.eu.

17. Does ERGA have a code of conduct?

Yes, check our Code of Conduct [here](#). If you have questions or concerns about our code of conduct, please reach out to the ELSI committee at elsi@erga-biodiversity.eu.

II. ERGA at the Regional and National levels

18. I checked the website and my country is not yet represented in the [ERGA Council](#).

Can I apply to become part of the council representing my country?

Yes, we are happy to welcome new countries to the Council and hope one day to count on representatives from all European countries! Please refer to the [Governance Document](#) for more details on how to join the council as a representative of your country.

19. How can I connect with other members of ERGA in my country?

To interact with the ERGA Community in your country, please contact your country council representative through the country email available [here](#).

Some countries have national initiatives already in place, here you can check some of our [regional partner projects](#).

III. ERGA Committees

20. What are the ERGA Committees?

The [ERGA Committees](#) are groups of members interested in a particular topic from the genome generation to the application process. These are informal groups and anyone is welcome to join! ERGA currently includes 10 committees:

Table 1: Overview of the ERGA Committees

		Email
SSP	Sampling & Sample Processing	samples@erga-biodiversity.eu
SAC	Sequencing & Assembly	assembly@erga-biodiversity.eu
Annotation	Annotation	annotation@erga-biodiversity.eu
DAC	Data Analysis	analysis@erga-biodiversity.eu
ITIC	IT & Infrastructure	itinfra@erga-biodiversity.eu
CS	Citizen Science	citizenscience@erga-biodiversity.eu
TKT	Training & Knowledge Transfer	training@erga-biodiversity.eu
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, Social Issues	elsi@erga-biodiversity.eu
SC	Social Justice Committee	socialjustice@erga-biodiversity.eu
Media	Media & Communications	media@erga-biodiversity.eu

To learn more about each committee, [head to their page on our website](#). To join their next meeting, simply send them an email and say you would like to participate.

21. How are the ERGA Committees structured?

Anyone is welcome to join the meetings and become a committee *Participant* - with no obligation to attend all the meetings or follow-up on actions. To keep the committees running each one also has appointed *Chair(s)*, responsible for guiding and representing the committee; a *Coordinator*, which provides organisational and administrative support; and a small group of committee *Steering members*. To learn more about the formal structure of the committees, please refer to the [Governance Document](#).

22. How can I stay informed about the activities of a particular committee?

The best way is by joining their monthly meetings (check Table 1 above). You can also join the committee's channel on [KeyBase](#). Some committees also have a dedicated mailing list. If interested, you can write to the committee's address and ask to be included.

23. How can I become a Committee Steering Member?

If you wish to take a more committed role in a committee, you can ask to be included as a member of the Steering group. In general, Steering members should attend all the meetings and actively engage with the committee's activities.

ERGA Glossary

The [ERGA Glossary](#) provides explanations about terms and acronyms often used within ERGA and in the context of Biodiversity Genomics.